

1 **Elavl family RNA-binding molecules are required for transformation of human cells.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 Elavl1 functioned early in transformation, at an intermediate or transition phase prior to induction of
7 transformation proper. Elavl1 operated in a transcriptional network with interaction partners ILF3, SLBP,
8 DNMT1, and Mad212. Targeting of *Elavl1* in transformed cells highlights this position, and thus genes
9 induced or repressed by Elavl1 depletion recall molecules important early in transition to transformed
10 state.

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